

THE ROLE OF “PADARKUSH” IN UZBEK DRAMATURGY AND THEATRE

(analysis and interpretations)

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Annotation: This article examines the history of the creation and publication of the drama “*Padarkush*,” which was first written and staged in the literature of the peoples of Central Asia by Mahmud Khoja Behbudiy. It also discusses the real-life and artistic foundations that formed the basis of the drama, as well as the analyses and interpretations offered by Uzbek and foreign scholars of Uzbek studies.

Keywords: Mahmud Khoja Behbudiy, patricide motif, early drama, Jadid dramaturgy, national drama, theatre, interpretation and research.

“**PADARKUSH**” is a national dramatic work by Mahmud Khoja Behbudiy. This drama was written in 1911 and published in 1913.

The American scholar of Uzbek studies E. Olworth wrote the following about the drama “*Padarkush*” in his research: “B., one of the founders of Jadid literature, created the first national dramatic work among the writers of Central Asia. Before that, not a single work in the drama genre had been produced in this region in either Turkic or Persian. This became Behbudiy’s greatest contribution to literature. In addition, he created prose works for his compatriots that were not overly complex, either linguistically or structurally, and were well suited to the new conditions and environment. For Behbudiy’s time, this was a major event.” [8. 2009, P. 107.] Previously, it had been regarded as the first work written in the Uzbek language in the history of Uzbek dramaturgy. However, following the observations of E. Olworth, it became clear that “*Padarkush*” should be understood as the first dramatic work created in the literature of the peoples of Central Asia.

The drama “*Padarkush*” has been analyzed by dozens of scholars such as B. Kasimov, N. Karimov, S. Ahmad, Sh. Rizaev, S. Tulaganova, and M. Kuchkarova. It has also been studied by foreign Uzbekists such as E. Olworth and T. Kojaogli. According to the research of Uzbek theatre scholars, it is noted that the Kokand playwright Abdurauf Samadov wrote the drama “*Mahramlar*” (*Kinsmen*). Uzbek theatre scholars point out that “*Mahramlar*” was published in 1911, before Behbudiy’s “*Padarkush*.” According to Miyon Buzruk Salihov, Cho‘lpon considered “*Mahramlar*” to be “the first Uzbek play.” “It is true that Samadov’s play ‘*Mahramlar*’ is a work taken from Uzbek life and written in the Uzbek language for the first time. In history, its author Samadov remains the writer who initiated the writing of Uzbek plays. This is because he adapted his Tatar-language play ‘*O‘luklar*’ into Uzbek under the title “*Mahramlar*” and managed to publish it in 1911. However, the issue here is not about granting the honor of being ‘first’ to a particular work, but about reflecting the history of the growth and development of local theatrical forces. From this perspective, “*Mahramlar*” cannot be presented as the first play written by local forces, because it was staged only after the staging of ‘*Padarkush*’.” [7. 2022, P. 126.]

Academician N. Karimov, for these reasons, concludes as noted by Miyon Buzruk Solihov that the play “*Mahramlar*” had originally been written in Uzbek under the title “*O‘liklar*” (*The Dead*). Nevertheless, he emphasizes that the fact that Uzbek theatre troupes had only begun to be

formed and that the play was staged by them after “*Padarkush*” does not allow it to be considered the first Uzbek drama.

“*Padarkush*” is the first work by Behbudiy written in the Uzbek language and staged for the first time on the Uzbek stage, being presented to the public. It is also possible to recognize Behbudiy as the first playwright who laid the foundation of Uzbek dramaturgy. The play “*Mahramlar*,” written by Abdurauf Samadov, was staged after “*Padarkush*.” In the cultural life of Turkestan at that time, no other theatrical performance was as popular as the staging of “*Padarkush*.”

There are also differing opinions regarding when “*Padarkush*” was written. For example, A. Samoylovich, in his article “The Dramatic Literature of the Sarts,” published in the Petrograd journal Bulletin of the Imperial Society of Orientalists (1917, No. 5), stated that Mahmudxo‘ja Behbudiy wrote “*Padarkush*” in 1911.

The Russian theatre scholar B. Pestovskiy does not clarify the exact year in which Behbudiy wrote the drama “*Padarkush*.” In presenting his views, he relies on the opinions of the Russian orientalist Vyatkin and suggests that Behbudiy was influenced by seeing a stage version of Denis Fonvizin’s play “*The Minor*” (“*Nedorosl*”) in Russian theatre, which inspired him to write “*Padarkush*.”

Such views were passed along like a chain in the opinions of Russian missionaries and their followers, repeatedly echoing one another. Therefore, the firm and objective response of Academician N. Karimov to such one-sided perspectives is particularly appropriate: “This situation is not accidental. Russian missionaries and their followers of the 1930s-50s, and even up to the 1960s, tended to ignore the national roots of modern Uzbek literature and art, claiming that almost all spheres of Uzbek culture had emerged under the influence of Russian culture.” [7. 2022, P. 129.]

Of course, it is reasonable to assume that in creating the drama “*Padarkush*,” Behbudiy was influenced by Russian, Azerbaijani, Tatar, and Turkish playwrights and their stage works. However, attributing it solely to the influence of a single Russian playwright Denis Fonvizin’s “*The Minor*” (“*Nedorosl*”) is a one-sided and inaccurate interpretation. Moreover, the image of the ignorant child who becomes a patricide, as well as the theme of child upbringing depicted in “*Padarkush*,” is more plausibly drawn from the real life of Turkestan at the beginning of the 20th century. As another Behbudiy scholar, S. Ahmad, writes: “The interest of Mahmudxo‘ja Behbudiy in theatrical art and his attempt at dramaturgy was not accidental. Those who look at the history of world civilization particularly the theatre traditions of ancient Greece, Europe, and China recognize that theatre was often first developed by religious figures. Therefore, it is no coincidence that this great educator turned to this field. As a cultured individual, Behbudiy became acquainted with theatrical art during his travels to Russia and Turkey. Through the press materials available to him, he took an interest in the role of theatre in various countries. He also watched the performances of Azerbaijani touring troupes that visited Samarkand. Most importantly, he had a deep understanding of the place and social function of theatre in human society.” [1. 2024. P. 228.]

The stage work “*Padarkush*” by Behbudiy made a significant contribution to the development of theatrical art among the people in the fullest sense. In this drama, Behbudiy artistically demonstrates through a simple real-life situation how ignorance and lack of education can strike a fatal blow to the future of a nation. Speaking about the main artistic idea of “*Padarkush*,” N. Karimov notes: “At the beginning of the 20th century in Turkestan, there were not few fathers who neglected the upbringing of their children, as well as young people who spent their formative years among idle, lazy, and pleasure-seeking wealthy youths. In ‘*Padarkush*,’

Behbudiy aimed not only to depict such fathers, but also to show that the lives of such children could end in tragedy, thereby warning both groups and, in general, Uzbek society of the early 20th century.” [7. Karimov, 2022. P. 130.]

According to Miyon Buzruk Solihov, “*Padarkush*” was completed between 1911 and 1912. Naturally, after receiving feedback from specialists, Behbudiy revised and refined the work.

In order for the drama “*Padarkush*” to be published as a book, Behbudiy added a dedication stating that the work was devoted to the 100th anniversary of the Battle of Borodino. According to theatre and literary scholars, Behbudiy resorted to such a strategy in order to gain the approval of the Tsarist authorities. To publish “*Padarkush*,” Behbudiy obtained permission from the governorship in the Caucasus. In Behbudiy studies, debates surrounding this issue have also been clarified. According to the research of B. Do‘stqoraev, the military governor of Samarkand in 1912-1913 was Major General Ilya Odishelidze. He promised to help secure permission for the publication of “*Padarkush*.” On February 10, 1913, by order of the Turkestan Governor-General Samsonov, Odishelidze was called away on a two-month leave. He took the manuscript of “*Padarkush*” with him to his homeland, Georgia. Due to illness, he extended his leave for another two months and remained there. Although he returned to duty on May 16, even before the end of his leave, he did not immediately deal with the publication issue. It later became known that he had submitted the manuscript to the Tiflis Committee for Press Affairs. After returning to Samarkand and following repeated requests from Behbudiy, Odishelidze was compelled to contact the committee. Eventually, he secured permission from this body for the publication of “*Padarkush*.” Thus, the publication of “*Padarkush*” went through a long and complicated process.

The first scenes of “*Padarkush*” were published in the newspaper “*Turon*.” Naturally, staging the play in a literary environment where professional theatre actors had not yet been formed placed Behbudiy in many difficult situations. Therefore, in response to a letter published in the 51st issue of the journal “*Oyna*” in 1913, Behbudiy wrote: “There are no people to perform it. Indeed, in Turkestan there are no idle people who would work for the public! Nor are there individuals who would step onto the stage and engage in play-acting.” Only when ten people are found who are willing to take on the burden of acting will it be staged.” [5. Karimov, 2022. P. 132.]

A contemporary of Behbudiy, Abdulhamid Azamat, in his article “*My Memories of Behbudiy*,” wrote the following about the role of “*Padarkush*” in Uzbek dramaturgy and the process of its staging: “Among the services of Behbudiy afandi that I know among the people, the closest is that he gave birth to a local national theatre in Turkestan. In this regard, it would not be wrong to call him the father of Turkestan theatre. These days, the theatre troupe established in Samarkand has taken the name “Behbudiy,” and this is a very appropriate act.”

“Behbudiy afandi, on the one hand, by writing his book ‘*Padarkush*,’ laid the foundation for a new literature in Turkestan; on the other hand, through this very work, he cultivated forces from among the local people who would work in the world of theatre, thereby giving birth to Turkestan theatre.” [4. Abdulhamid Azamat, P. 247.]

According to the testimony of Abdulhamid Azamat, who witnessed the staging process of “*Padarkush*,” the issue of actors especially forming a cast capable of performing female roles was extremely difficult at that time. Moreover, children did not yet understand the profession of acting, and many avoided it out of fear of being disowned by their parents. Nevertheless, despite such challenging conditions, a group of actors was eventually assembled to stage “*Padarkush*.” Rehearsals for the performance began, and male actors were compelled to perform female roles, as no women from the local population dared to take on such parts. Furthermore, performing a role was not a simple task – it required both talent and skill.

Mahmudxo‘ja Behbudiy addressed the local people – particularly the actors gathered to stage “*Padarkush*” with a speech about the significance of theatrical art. He explained to them the

importance of theatre, emphasizing the educational, moral, and enlightening value of stage works, which serve as a mirror reflecting society back to the people.

Thus, on January 15, 1914, in the new city part of Samarkand, the first Uzbek drama “*Padarkush*” was staged for the first time. Abdulhamid Azamat recalls the popularity of “*Padarkush*” among the people as follows: “Due to the shortage of tickets, people who remained outside left considerable amounts of money at the ticket office just to get inside the theatre. Considering the time, the performance was staged quite well. The audience was very satisfied. The young people who organized this performance were greatly inspired and, without dispersing, even went to the city of Kokand, where they successfully staged the play. After these performances, the reading room and library of the old city of Samarkand were somewhat revived financially. Thus, theatrical art came into being in Turkestan. Even though there were no organized stage professionals, amateurs began to unite three or four times a year to stage performances.” [4. Abdulhamid Azamat, P. 247.]

These stage works were written based on the everyday life of the local population of Turkestan. Accordingly, plays such as Hoji Mu’in Shukrullo’s “*Mazluma xotun*” (*Oppressed woman*), “*Eski maktab, yangi maktab*” (Old school, new school), and “*Ko’knori*” (*Poppy*) Abdulla Badriy’s “*Juvonmarg*” (*Died young*) and “*Ahmoq*” (Fool) as well as Nusratullo Kudratullo o’g’li’s tragedy “*To’y*” (Wedding) were created. These dramas were staged through the efforts of their authors and their close associates.

In his article “*Tiyotr nadur*” (*What is theatre?*), Behbudiy wrote about the successful staging of “*Padarkush*” as follows: “The humble author wrote ‘*Padarkush*,’ and in the past month of February it was staged in Samarkand, Kokand, Bukhara, Tashkent, and Kattakurgan by volunteers for the benefit of the nation. Within four or five evenings, four to five thousand sums were collected and donated for the benefit of schools.” [4. Behbudiy, P. 16.]

As the author emphasizes, the funds generated from the staged performances of “*Padarkush*” were not used by Behbudiy and his associates for their personal needs. Instead, the proceeds were spent on addressing the shortcomings of Jadid schools.

Scholars have also discussed whether the tragic event underlying the drama “*Padarkush*” has a real-life basis. The interpretation of the tragic incident depicted in the drama is, in fact, mentioned in the memoir “*Courts during the Tsarist period*,” published in the newspaper “*Zarafshan*” by Behbudiy’s contemporary Hukandboy Abdukhalik o’g’li. He writes: “At one time in Samarkand, it had become common to kill wealthy men. In order to inherit their property, they were often murdered by their own sons. One such wealthy man was Mirvafabay, whose sons had grown up almost like enemies toward him. One of his sons, named Abdulla, even gave money to thieves in order to have his father killed...” [5. Karimov, 2022. P. 135.]

Another writer, Hasan Irfan, also recalls in his work a real-life case similar to the events depicted in “*Padarkush*.” He narrates an account about a Samarkand merchant, Mirsharafbay, who was killed by his own son, and how the patricidal son squandered his father’s inheritance in a short time and ended up in misery. The protagonist of the novel is the author himself, who recalls the events portrayed in a play he had watched: “In the play, a story was told that we had heard from our teacher Ismatulla. It was a strange and instructive story – one that makes your heart shrink. The son of a wealthy man falls into the company of idle and pleasure-seeking people. Then, in order to gain his father’s inheritance, he kills him. However, before long, he wastes all the wealth left by his father and falls into beggary...”

“...The act of patricide shook everyone and created a deeply unpleasant mood among the audience. The spectators groaned in distress, cursed the criminal, and did not even applaud the actor who played the role of the perpetrator...” [5. Karimov, 2022. P. 135.]

N. Karimov considers the above excerpts taken from real-life accounts and literary works as the life-based and artistic foundations for the creation of the drama “*Padarkush*.” Indeed, there is

little doubt that the tragic fate of an uneducated child who becomes a patricide in “*Padarkush*” was inspired by numerous similar real-life incidents that occurred in Turkestan.

The Jadid scholar Sh. Rizaev writes about the “tavern scene” depicted in the drama “*Padarkush*” as follows: “In ‘*Padarkush*,’ another serious indication that tragedies are occurring due to social degradation can be understood from the ‘tavern scene.’ By depicting three or four strong, young local men sitting together with the adolescent Toshmuradboyvachcha, drinking alcohol and being in a drunken state, Behbudiy sought to emphasize that alcohol consumption and taverns introduced from outside and taking root in Turkestan had become a harmful mass phenomenon among Muslim youth.”

“...The local population, by drawing closer to the Russians and learning to speak Russian, adopted not only aspects of their outward way of life but also many of its negative traits such as a frivolous lifestyle and the consumption of wine and beer. This even extended to the educated members of society and religious figures...” [5. Karimov, 2022. B. 136.]

Of course, adopting the negative traits of another culture is a harmful tendency. In the drama “*Padarkush*,” the main character Toshmurad, having become accustomed to a life of indulgence and drinking, befriends street hooligans such as Tangrikul and Davlat with the small amount of money given by his father. They spend their time in the tavern of an Armenian named Artyom, engaging in reckless pleasure, and ultimately Toshmurad becomes the murderer of his own father. The wealthy father, already around fifty years old, does not concern himself with his son’s education. Instead, he simply gives him money whenever he asks, thereby enabling him to become idle, wayward, and addicted to pleasure. He rejects both the progressive-minded mullah and the educated intellectual the reformist Muslim of the time. Relying on his servant Khayrullo, he assumes that one can live without knowledge and education. As a result, he meets a tragic death. His family falls into deep misfortune: his son and his companions are exiled, and the entire family is shattered. It is precisely this seemingly small yet deeply tragic story that is portrayed in “*Padarkush*,” created by Mahmud Khoja Behbudiy.

S. Ahmad writes: “In the work, the tavern depicted as a place of moral corruption and the destruction of national ethics along with the prostitute Liza and the poisonous drinks adorning the large tables, are presented as part of the ‘culture’ brought to Turkestan by Russia. Those who are raised in the immoral environment of such establishments are convincingly shown to become thieves, murderers, and depraved individuals.” [1. Ahmad S, 2024. P. 240-241.]

In the small-scale stage work “*Padarkush*,” Mahmud Khoja Behbudiy artistically portrays the negligence of local wealthy classes through the tragedy of a rich man and his narrow-minded son, Toshmurad. S. Ahmad also notes that the transfer of commercial activity into the hands of outsiders – Armenians and Jews is reflected through the tavern scene in the drama. Thus, “*Padarkush*” can justifiably be regarded as a work written in line with the program of Jadid enlightenment thinkers. This is especially evident in the words of the character Ziyoli in the drama:

“It is ignorance and lack of proper upbringing that have brought us to ruin, made us homeless, scattered, and subjugated. Homelessness, wandering, oppression, poverty, and humiliation all are the fruits and consequences of ignorance and lack of education. Nations that have progressed in the world have advanced through knowledge. Those who are oppressed and weakened are so because of ignorance.”

S. Ahmad clearly points out that two major tragedies are depicted in the drama “*Padarkush*”: “Through the drama ‘*Padarkush*,’ the great educator showed that the people were under two kinds of oppression. The first was national ignorance superstition, failure to value knowledge, and, in simple terms, the people’s inability to reflect on their own condition. The second was the harmful influences and political pressure brought by the colonial Tsarist government and its missionaries. Because of these vices, the nation risked being trampled by others and even disappearing as a

people. Therefore, in order to preserve itself, it was necessary to develop modern and civilized regulations and legal frameworks.” [1. Ahmad S, 2024. P. 244-245.]

Starting from 1913, the drama “*Padarkush*” was staged in many cities and villages of Turkestan. However, no other play achieved the same level of popularity as Mahmud Khoja Behbudiy’s “*Padarkush*.” The tragic story depicted in the drama drawn from everyday life in Turkestan together with themes such as parental neglect in child upbringing, ignorance, lack of education, and a murder resulting from such conditions, deeply affected ordinary people through its stage performance. For this reason, Behbudiy’s contemporary Abdulhamid Azamat wrote: “Having watched such works on stage, the audience—who had come to understand theatre in a simple and clear way was later confused after the revolution by various obscure concepts. They were suddenly confronted with plays drawn from different national lifestyles. Some would write something in just two hours and put it on stage, while others presented works like ‘*Abu Muslim*,’ ‘*Chin sevish*,’ and ‘*Zahhoki moron*,’ which were suitable only for the second stage of Turkestan theatre. Such works, too complex for the conditions of the time, placed both the young theatre practitioners and the still inexperienced audience in a difficult situation.” [4. Abdulhamid Azamat, P. 247.]

In Samarkand, the staging of “*Padarkush*” was directly overseen by Behbudiy himself. Permission from the governor was obtained for the performance. On January 15, 1914, “*Padarkush*” was staged in Samarkand and presented to the public. The performance featured actors such as Abdusalom Abdurahim oqli, Abbos Muznib, Mardonkuli Shomuhhammad oqli, Muhiddin Juraboy oqli, Abdulla Badriy, Muhammad Aminjon Niyoziy, and Ahmadjon Shamsuddinov.

The drama “*Padarkush*” was simple enough to be appealing to the common people, and was liked by everyone in terms of its touching and tragic tone. However, the dramas created by Fitrat’s professional pen and their stage versions did not sink into the hearts of the people like “*Padarkush*”, testifies a contemporary of M. Behbudi.

Under the influence of “*Padarkush*,” a whole generation of figures in Uzbek stage culture directors and playwrights emerged. Among them were Muhammad Rahim Toji in Samarkand; Nizomiddin Khojaev, Badriddin Alamov, Mannon Uygur, and Abdurahmon Ismoilzoda in Tashkent; as well as Toshkhoja Ashurkhoja, Hamza Hakimzoda Niyoziy, and Yulchi Egamberdiev in Kokand who became prominent representatives of this field. In addition, creative collaborations were established with accomplished directors such as Aliaskar Askarov Hoji Dadash oqli and Sidki Ruhullo from Azerbaijan, as well as Zoki Boyazidskiy-Valeev from the Tatar theatre tradition. On the initiative of Munavvar qori Abdurashidkhanov, Abdulla Avloniy, and Ubaydulla Khujaev, the “*Turon*” troupe was established, laying the foundation for the national theatre. At the same time, Uzbek national theatre criticism began to develop in the press. In particular, critics such as Mirmulla Shermuhammad, Mirmuhsin Shermuhammad, Chulpan, and Gozi Yunus emerged.

M. Behbudiy’s drama “*Padarkush*” laid the foundation for the emergence of Uzbek national dramaturgy and theater art. “*Padarkush*” as the first national stage work deeply penetrated the hearts of the people. At the same time, this first dramatic work determined the socio-political and artistic-ideological direction of the Uzbek national theater.

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